

Spider diversity of the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve, Gauteng Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: A first report on the diversity of the spiders at the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve in the Gauteng Province, South Africa. It is about 220,000 years old and one of the best-preserved terrestrial meteorite impact craters in the world. The reserve covers about 2,000 hectares and includes the crater itself, the central saline lake, and the surrounding bushveld. It is home to a diverse group of spiders, and 23 spider families represented by 86 genera and 110 species have been collected. The Salticidae (18 species), Araneidae (17 species) and Thomisidae (13 species) are the most species-rich families. Each species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status are provided. Most of the species collected have been photographed and are available on Naturalist.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) is dedicated to documenting and unifying information on arachnids in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). SANSA projects are underway in the different provinces, focusing on protected areas and urban and suburban areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

Gauteng is by far the smallest province, covering only 1.4% of South Africa. The province falls within both the Savanna and the highly threatened Grassland Biome, and approximately 83% of the province comprises Highveld Grassland vegetation types, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa. Gauteng is the most populous province in South Africa, with about 25.3% of the country's population living there according to the 2024 mid-year estimates by Statistics South Africa. The province has the highest population density and the highest urbanisation levels. Consequently, biodiversity in the province is highly threatened by industrialisation, mining, agriculture, and especially urbanisation, the latter driven by current high demand for land and basic services (Pfab, 2001).

Essentially, the successful conservation of biodiversity within Gauteng will require identifying priority areas where development and habitat transformation and fragmentation should be discouraged, and where conservation efforts should be focused.

Some results from SANSA show that in Gauteng, a total of 350 sites have been sampled to date, yielding more than 6800 records, 52 families, 250 genera, and 563 spp. (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). A total of 24 protected areas have been sampled in Gauteng, including research stations, reserves and a botanical garden. Although relatively well sampled, only nine checklist papers have been published to date, mainly from nature reserves, research stations and a botanical garden (Table 1).

We report on our present knowledge of the diversity of the spiders found at the Tswaing Meteorite Crater. About 220,000 years ago, a blazing, stony meteorite approximately 50 m in diameter slammed into Earth's crust, forming a huge crater 1,13 km in diameter and initially 200 m deep. It is one of the best-preserved terrestrial meteorite impact craters in the world. Tswaing also has a saline lake fed by an underground spring (Reimold *et al.*, 1999).

This is the first report on the diversity of the spiders at the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve (TMCR). The data were extracted from the SANSA database and include the results of ad hoc collecting during visits to the area. Each species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status are provided.

Figure 1. The Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve covers about 2,000 hectares and includes the crater itself, the central saline lake, and surrounding bushveld.

STUDY AREA

The Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve (TMCR) is a 2000-hectare protected area situated 47 km north of Pretoria (-25.24S, 28.04E) in the Gauteng Province of South Africa (Fig. 2). It is an impact crater with the astrobleme 1.13 km in diameter and 100 m deep. The age is estimated to be 220,000 ± 52,000 years (Pleistocene). It falls within the Savanna Biome and comprises mainly acacia bushveld, broad-leafed and riverine vegetation. Tswaing Lake, in the center of the crater, is 100 m in diameter and is filled with rain and spring water. The lake once contained high concentrations of salt and soda ash that were mined for 44 years until 1956. The factory's remains still stand near the lake (Reimold *et al.*, 1999).

Figure 2. Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve in Gauteng.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collecting methods, identification, and voucher specimens: The first SANSA surveys started in 2007, and the first author identified the specimens. All the sampled material is deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (non-Acari) (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection. During a trip to the TMCR in February 2017, several adult spiders were sampled and photographed by the second author, who is now available on iNaturalis.

Endemicity value: The endemicity values for each species are provided in Table 4. Seven endemicity categories are recognized:

- 6—species are only known from the type locality (TMCR).
- 5—species known only from the Gauteng Province (GE).
- 4—species are known from the Gauteng Province and an adjoining province.
- 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE).
- 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa (STHE).
- 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE).
- 0—also known from outside the Afrotropical Region.

TABLE 1. Spider diversity of nine sites sampled in the Gauteng Province, with the total number of families (F), genera (G) and species (SPP) recorded.

LOCALITY	F	G	SPP	REFERENCE
Roodeplaat Research Station (crop)	14	28	31	Dippenaar-Schoeman (1979)
Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (1)	27	82	95	Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (1989)
Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (2)	40	161	245	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (2024)
Rietondale Research Station	21	41	55	Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)
Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve	31	85	103	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (2022)
Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve	37	113	142	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl (2023)
Groenkloof Nature Reserve	35	84	112	Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2023)
Pretoria National Botanical Garden	36	113	152	Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2024)
Irene grassland survey	39	150	257	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (2025)
Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve	23	86	110	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (in press)

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or known only from type locality, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (data deficient).

Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 are considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC. Species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve (TMCR) with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	G	SPP.	FAMILIES	G	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Philodromidae	1	3
Araneidae	11	17	Pisauridae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Salticidae	16	18
Clubionidae	1	1	Selenopidae	2	2
Corinnidae	3	3	Stasimopidae	1	1
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	7	9	Theridiidae	6	7
Idiopidae	4	4	Thomisidae	10	13
Linyphiidae	3	3	Uloboridae	1	1
Lycosidae	5	5	Zodariidae	4	5
Oxyopidae	3	9		86	110

Figures 3–4. Undetermined species. 3. Philodromidae (*Philodromus* sp.). 4. Oxyopidae (*Oxyopes* sp.). Credits: Peter Webb.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 110 species, 86 genera, from 23 families, were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). The spider diversity sampled across nine localities as part of the SANSА Gauteng survey project is listed in Table 1. The data show that on average, 31 families, 95 genera and 132 species are sampled per site. The number of spiders sampled at the TMCR is a little lower than the average.

Family diversity: Of the 23 spider families collected from TMCR (Tables 2 & 4), the three most species-rich families are Salticidae (18 spp.), Araneidae (17 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (13 spp.) and Gnaphosidae (14 spp.). Five families are represented by singletons.

A photo gallery of some of the spiders sampled at the TMNR is provided (Figs 3–32). In the Araneidae, the species *Araniella cucurbitina* (Clerck, 1757) (Figs 5–6) was recorded for the first time from South Africa, and two colour morphs of *Cyrtophora citricola* (Figs 9–10) were sampled.

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve (TMCR).

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	2	1.8
Data deficient DD	1	0.9
Least concern LC	106	96.4
Vulnerable	1	0.9
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	18	16.4
1 – African endemics (AE)	51	46.4
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	17	15.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	20	18.2
4 – South African endemics (SAE):	1	0.9
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	1	0.9
6 – Type locality	0	0

Conservation status: One Oxyopidae species (Fig. 4) and one Philodromidae species (Fig. 3) are possibly new and were not evaluated. *Stasimopus hewitti* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 (Fig. 7) is a Gauteng-endemic species described from the Wonderboom district. It is presently recorded from only seven locations, and as ongoing habitat loss within this species' range due to urbanisation continues, it is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion. The remaining 150 species have a wide distribution, are not known to face threats, and are listed as Least Concern. *Cheiracanthium dippenarae* Lotz, 2007 is known only from one sex and is under-sampled; it is Data Deficient.

Endemism: Eighteen species (16.4%) sampled at TMCR have a distribution wider than Africa, while 51 species (46.4%) are African endemics (AE), 17 species (15.5%) are Southern African endemics, and 22 species (20%) are South African endemics (Table 3). *Stasimopus hewitti* (Fig. 7), a trapdoor spider, is a Gauteng endemic, and the gnaphosid *Nomisia transvaalica* Dalmas, 1921 (Fig. 31) is a near-Gauteng endemic.

Figures 5–6. *Araniella cucurbitina* first record from South Africa
Credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 7. *Stasimopus hewitti* listed as Vulnerable. Credit: David Jacobs.

Figure 8. *Harpactira hamiltoni*. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 9–32. Spiders from the Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve. 9. *Cyrtophora citricola*. 10. *Cyrtophora citricola*. 11. *Cyphalonotus larvatus*. 12. *Hypsosinga lithyphantoides*. 13. *Nemoscolus cotti*. 14. *Neoscona moreli*. 15. *Leucauge levanderi*. 16. *Oxyopes bothai*. 17. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 18. *Menemerus eburnensis*. 19. *Natta horizontalis*. 20. *Pseudicius gracilis*. 21. *Rhene lingularis*. 22. *Hyllus argyrotorus*. 23. *Parajotus obscurifemoratus*. 24. *Stenaelurillus guttiger*. 25. *Mystaria savannensis*. 26. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*. 27. *Runcinia flavida*. 28. *Thomisus scrupeus*. 29. *Xysticus natalensis*. 30. *Nomisia transvaalica*. 31. *Evippoma squamulatum*. 32. *Systemoplacis vandami*. Credits: Peter Webb.

TABLE 4: Spiders of Tswaing Meteorite Crater Reserve listing their endemicy (END), conservation status (CON), country endemicy (CEN) LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated.

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN	SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
1. FAMILY AGELENIDAE				10. FAMILY LINYPHIIDAE			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
2. FAMILY ARANEIDAE				<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Araniella cucurbitina</i> (Clerck, 1757)(Figs 5–6)	0	LC	C	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 11)	1	LC	AE	11. FAMILY LYCOSIDAE			
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775) (Figs 9–10)	0	LC	C	<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	<i>Eviopomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 31)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947 (Fig. 13)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hypsosinga pygmaea</i> (Sundevall, 1831)	0	LC	C	<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	<i>Spiniculosa crassipalpis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933 (Fig. 13)	2	LC	STHE	12. FAMILY OXYOPIIDAE			
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863) (Fig. 14)	0	LC	C	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona quincasea</i> Roberts, 1983	1	LC	AE	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	C	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 17)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C	<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. (undetermined) (Fig. 4)			NE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
3. FAMILY CHEIRACANTHIDAE				13. FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiracanthium dippenarae</i> Lotz, 2007	3	DD	SAE	<i>Philodromus partitus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
4. FAMILY CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Philodromus</i> sp. (undetermined) (Fig. 3)			NE
<i>Clubiona pupillaris</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	14. FAMILY PISAURIDAE			
5. FAMILY CORINNIDAE				<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	<i>Maypacijs roeweri</i> Blandin, 1975	1	LC	AE
<i>Corinnomma semiglabrum</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	15. FAMILY SALTICIDAE			
<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
6. FAMILY CYATHOLIPIDAE				<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ulwembua denticulata</i> Griswold, 1987	3	LC	SAE	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
7. FAMILY CYRTAUCHENIIDAE				<i>Helafricanus pistaciae</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ancylotrypa nuda</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
8. FAMILY GNAPHOSIDAE				<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	<i>Menemerus eburnensis</i> Berland & Millot, 1941 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
<i>Haplodrassus lophognathus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Mogrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
<i>Haplodrassus splendens</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879 (Fig. 19)	1	LC	AE
<i>Leptodrassex murphyi</i> Haddad & Booyesen, 2022	2	LC	STHE	<i>Parajotus obscurofemoratus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 23)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nomisia transvaalica</i> Dalmás, 1921	4	LC	SAE	<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011 (Fig. 20)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C	<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011 (Fig. 21)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011(Fig. 20)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 30)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 24)	2	LC	STHE
9. FAMILY IDIOPIDAE				<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Ctenolophus cregoei</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Gorgyrella schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	3	LC	SAE	<i>Trapezocephalus transvaalicus</i> (Simon, 1901)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Idiops monticola</i> Hewitt, 1916	3	LC	SAE	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE				

SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
16. FAMILY SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anypops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	0	LC	C
17. FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE			
<i>Stasimopus hewitti</i> Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 (Fig. 7)	5	VU	SAE
18. FAMILY TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901) (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
19. FAMILY THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902 (Fig. 8)	3	LC	SAE
20. FAMILY THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Argyrodes argyrodes</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	0	LC	C
<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
21. FAMILY THOMISIDAE			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Mystaria savannensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938 (Fig. 29)	2	LC	STHE
22. FAMILY ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
23. FAMILY ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores triarmatus</i> Lessert, 1929	1	LC	AE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916) (Fig. 32)	3	LC	SAE

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